

Synthesis and biological evaluation of some 2-amino-5-nitrothiazole derivatives of azetidine

Pushkal Samadhiya*, Ritu Sharma, S. K. Srivastava and S. D. Srivastava

Synthetic Organic Chemistry Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University (A Central University), Sagar-470 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : pushkalsamadhiya@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : A series of *N*-[2-(2-amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(substituted phenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxo-1-iminoazetidine, compounds **4(a-j)** have been synthesized from 2-amino-5-nitrothiazole as a starting material in four steps. The structure of all the synthesized compounds were confirmed by chemical and spectral analyses such as IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and FAB-Mass. All the synthesized compounds **4(a-j)** were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against some selected bacteria and fungi and antitubercular activity screened against *M. tuberculosis*.

Keywords : 2-Amino-5-nitrothiazole, 2-azetidinone, bioimportance.

Introduction

Thiazoles are one of the most intensively investigated classes of aromatic five membered heterocycles. Thiazole derivatives find a variety of application ranging from bacteriostatic^{1,2}, antifungal³, antiviral⁴. All these facts were driving force to develop novel thiazole derivatives with wide structure variations. Thus thiazole derivatives plays pivotal role in medicinal chemistry. As part of interest in heterocycles that have been explore for developing pharmaceutically important molecules. Moreover they have been studied extensively because of their ready accessibility, diverse chemical reactivity and broad spectrum of biological activity such as antimicrobial⁵, anti-inflammatory, analgesic⁶, antitubercular^{7,8}, antiproliferative⁹, anticonvulsant¹⁰, cytotoxicity¹¹. Azetidine ring containing heterocycle is a commonly occurring substructure in organic chemistry, found in a variety of structurally and biologically interesting natural products. Azetidine is a core structure in various synthetic pharmaceutical important molecules displayed a broad spectrum of biological activities, including antibacterial^{12,13}, antifungal¹⁴, anti-inflammatory¹⁵⁻¹⁷, anticonvulsant^{18,19}. Azetidine core plays an important role in various biological activities such as cardiovascular²⁰, antiviral activity²¹ etc. Here we are reporting synthesis of new series of *N*-[2-(2-amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(substituted phenyl)-3-chloro-2-

oxo-1-iminoazetidine, compounds **4(a-j)**. The structure of all the synthesized compounds were confirmed by chemical and spectral analyses such as IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and FAB-Mass. Compounds **4(a-j)** were screened for their antibacterial, antifungal and antitubercular activities.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(substituted phenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxo-1-iminoazetidine, compounds **4(a-j)** were synthesized in four steps (Fig. 1). 2-Amino-5-nitrothiazole on reaction with Cl(CH₂)₂Br at room temperature afforded 1-(2-chloroethyl)-2-amino-5-nitrothiazole, compound **1**. IR spectrum of compound **1** displayed absorptions at 1438 and 740 cm⁻¹ for (N-CH₂) and (C-Cl) respectively. The compound **1** on reaction with hydrazine hydrate at room temperature yielded *N*-[2-(2-amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]hydrazine, compound **2**. IR spectrum of compound **2** showed absorption for NH at 3375 cm⁻¹ while IR absorption of (C-Cl) has been disappeared. The ¹H NMR spectra of compound **2** displayed signal of (CH₂-NH) appear at δ 2.48 ppm. The compound **2** on further reaction with selected several substituted aromatic aldehydes produced *N*-[2-(2-amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-*N'*-[(substituted phenyl)methylidene]hydrazine, compounds **3(a-j)**, for the compounds **3(a-j)**

Reagents and conditions : (a) = 1-bromo-2-chloroethane; (b) = hydrazine hydrate; (c) = substituted benzaldehyde; (d) = triethylamine and chloroacetyl chloride

Fig. 1. Synthesis of compound 1, 2, 3(a-j) and 4(a-j).

characteristic absorption for Schiff base (N=CH) in IR spectra appeared in the range of 1556–1579 cm^{-1} and in the ^1H NMR spectra of compounds 3(a-j) signal found in the range of δ 7.84–8.13 ppm while in its ^{13}C NMR spectra a signal found at δ 153.3–158.6 ppm. In the ^1H NMR spectrum of compound 2 a broad signal of NH_2 has been disappeared at δ 5.46. The compounds 3(a-j) on treatment with ClCH_2COCl in the presence of Et_3N furnished final products compounds 4(a-j). In IR spectra of compounds 4(a-j), carbonyl group of β -lactam ring showed characteristic absorption in the range of 1742–1768 cm^{-1}

and ^1H NMR spectra two doublet appeared for (N-CH) and (CH-Cl) in the range of δ 4.72–4.96 and 4.23–4.38 ppm respectively but in ^{13}C NMR spectra two signal appeared for (N-CH) and (CH-Cl) in the range of δ 58.7–65.9 and 47.8–54.8 ppm respectively. The IR absorption and ^1H NMR signal of N=CH have been disappeared.

Biological study :

Antimicrobial and antitubercular data (as shown in Tables 1 and 2) revealed that all the synthesized compounds 4(a-j) have a structure activity relationship (SAR) because activity of compounds varies with substitution.

Table 1. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of compounds 4(a-j)

Compd.	<i>B. subtilis</i>		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>		<i>A. niger</i>		<i>A. flavus</i>		<i>C. albicans</i>	
	50 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm
4a	12	25	7	24	12	22	8	14	9	14	10	14
4b	15	33	12	30	16	34	13	23	10	22	14	24
4c	16	34	14	30	15	32	12	24	12	21	14	22
4d	17	33	11	31	14	29	12	22	10	21	13	21
4e	15	32	13	28	15	32	14	23	12	18	15	21
4f	16	31	15	27	15	29	12	21	11	17	14	21
4g	24	29	11	28	12	28	13	20	10	16	10	22
4h	25	28	10	25	13	29	9	19	9	15	12	22
4i	22	28	11	25	14	26	11	18	10	15	12	23
4j	25	28	12	26	12	26	14	17	11	16	12	20
Streptomycin	35	35	34	34	37	37	–	–	–	–	–	–
Griseofulvin	–	–	–	–	–	–	28	28	30	30	27	27

Table 2. Antitubercular activity of compounds **4(a-j)**

Compd.	% Activity		Compd.	% Activity	
	25	50		25	50
	ppm	ppm		ppm	ppm
4a	32	65	4f	40	79
4b	42	92	4g	39	75
4c	53	82	4h	42	82
4d	52	85	4i	37	83
4e	50	79	4j	38	87
Standard	100	100	Standard	100	100

Nitro group containing compounds (**4h**, **4i** and **4j**) showed higher activity than chloro (**4c**, **4d**), or bromo group containing compounds (**4e**, **4f**). Chloro and bromo derivatives also have higher activity than other compounds. On the basis of SAR, concluded that the activity of compounds depends on electron withdrawing nature of the substituted groups. The sequence of the activity is following : $\text{NO}_2 > \text{Cl} > \text{Br} > \text{H}$.

Conclusion :

Concluded that it is a successful route for the synthesis of compounds **1**, **2**, **3(a-j)** and **4(a-j)**. Antimicrobial and antitubercular data shown in Tables 1 and 2 revealed that the compounds **4c**, **4d**, **4e**, **4f**, **4h**, **4i** and **4j** displayed highly active compounds of the series, compounds **4b** and **4g** showed moderate activity and rest compounds showed less activity against all the strains compared with standard drugs.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Progress of reaction was monitored by silica gel-G coated TLC plates in MeOH : CHCl_3 system (1 : 9). The spot was visualized by exposing dry plate in iodine vapours. IR spectra were recorded in KBr disc on a Shimadzu 8201 PC, FTIR spectrophotometer (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) and ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were measured on a Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer in CDCl_3 at 300 and 75 MHz respectively using TMS as an internal standard. All chemical shifts were reported on δ scales. The FAB-Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX-102 mass spectrometer. Elemental analyses were performed on a Carlo Erba-1108 analyzer. The analytical data of all the compounds were highly satisfactory. For column chromatographic purification of the products, Merck silica Gel 60 (230-

400 mesh) was used. The reagent grade chemicals were purchased from the commercial sources and further purified before use.

Biological activities :

Antibacterial, antifungal and antitubercular activities :

A series of newly synthesized compounds were active against selected microorganisms. Inhibition zones were determined using the filter paper disc diffusion method and the concentrations have been used in ppm. Final synthesized compounds **4(a-j)** have been screened *in vitro* for their antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis*, *E. coli* and *S. aureus* and antifungal activity against *A. niger*, *A. flavus* and *C. albicans*. Standards for antibacterial and antifungal activity Streptomycin and Griseofulvin were used respectively. Standards also screened under the similar conditions for comparison. The antitubercular activity screened against the *M. tuberculosis*. For the antitubercular activity Isoniazid and Rifampicin were used as standard and also screened under the similar conditions. All concentrations of the compounds were given in ppm and results were given in Tables 1 and 2.

Method for the synthesis of compound 1 :

2-Amino-5-nitrothiazole (0.345 mol) and 1-bromo-2-chloroethane (0.345 mol) were dissolved in methanol at room temperature. The reaction mixture was continuously stirred on a magnetic stirrer for about 7 h. The product was filtered and purified over a column chromatography. The purified product was recrystallized from ethanol at room temperature to yield compound **1**.

1-(2-Chloroethyl)-2-amino-5-nitrothiazole (1) :

Yield : 58%, m.p. 160–165 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$: C, 28.92; H, 2.91; N, 20.23. Found : C, 28.88; H, 2.87; N, 20.18; IR (KBr) : 740 (C–Cl), 882 (C–S), 973 (C–NO), 1438 (N– CH_2), 1536 (NO_2), 1568 (C=C), 2888, 3075 (CH), 3384 (NH); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 2.42 (2H, t, J 7.50 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{-Cl}$), 3.14 (2H, t, J 7.50 Hz, N– CH_2), 7.18 (1H, s, C_4H of thiazole), 7.78 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 36.8 ($\text{CH}_2\text{-Cl}$), 44.1 (N– CH_2), 136.8 (C_4 of thiazole), 138.3 (C_5 of thiazole), 169.6 (C_2 of thiazole); Mass (FAB) : 207 M^+ .

Method for the synthesis of compound 2 :

Compound **1** (0.225 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.225 mol) were dissolved in methanol at room temperature.

The reaction mixture was continuously stirred on a magnetic stirrer for about 8 h. The product was filtered and purified over a column chromatography. The purified product was recrystallized from ethanol at room temperature to yield compound **2**.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]hydrazine (**2**) :

Yield : 72%, m.p. 145-150 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_5H_9N_5O_2S$: C, 29.55; H, 4.46; N, 34.46. Found : C, 29.50; H, 4.42; N, 34.41; IR (KBr) : 878 (C-N), 886 (C-S), 1339 (N-CH₂), 1528 (NO₂), 3375 (NH), 3488 (NH₂); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.48-2.53 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 2.92-2.97 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 5.46 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.16 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 7.63 (1H, s, NH), 8.12 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 36.7 (CH₂-NH), 44.7 (N-CH₂), 136.4 (C₄ of thiazole), 138.7 (C₅ of thiazole), 168.9 (C₂ of thiazole); Mass (FAB) : 203 M⁺.

General method for the synthesis of compounds 3(a-j) :

Compound **2** (0.033 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.033 mol) were dissolved in methanol at room temperature in the presence of 2-3 drops of glacial acetic acid and allowed to react. The reaction mixture was first continuously stirred on a magnetic stirrer for about 2-3 h followed by reflux on a steam bath for about 1.30-4.15 h. The products were cooled and filtered. The products were purified over a column chromatography and recrystallized from ethanol at room temperature to yield compound **3a**.

Compounds **3(b-j)** have also been synthesized by similar method as above.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-*N'*-[(phenyl)methylidene]hydrazine (**3a**) :

Yield : 62%, m.p. 153-155 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{13}N_5O_2S$: C, 49.47; H, 4.49; N, 24.03. Found : C, 49.41; H, 4.44; N, 23.96; IR (KBr) : 1559 (N=CH), 3369 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.43-2.50 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 2.94-2.99 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 7.28 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 3.43 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 3.94 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 7.78 (1H, s, NH), 7.89 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.19 (1H, s, NH), 6.41-7.13 (5H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 36.5 (CH₂-NH), 44.4 (N-CH₂), 134.7 (C₄ of thiazole), 139.6 (C₅ of thiazole), 153.6 (N=CH), 168.4 (C₂ of thiazole), 125.6, 128.8, 129.8, 137.9 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 291 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-*N'*-[(4-chlorophenyl)methylidene]hydrazine (**3b**) :

Yield : 62%, m.p. 166-167 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{12}N_5O_2SCl$: C, 44.24; H, 3.71; N, 21.49. Found : C, 44.20; H, 3.65; N, 21.40; IR (KBr) : 748 (C-Cl), 1568 (N=CH), 3370 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.59-2.63 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 2.98-3.02 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 7.36 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 7.73 (1H, s, NH), 7.99 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.17 (1H, s, NH), 6.67-7.82 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 35.4 (CH₂-NH), 49.4 (N-CH₂), 138.5 (C₄ of thiazole), 141.6 (C₅ of thiazole), 154.8 (N=CH), 173.7 (C₂ of thiazole), 126.6, 127.8, 128.7, 130.8, 135.7, 138.9 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 326 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-*N'*-[(3-chlorophenyl)methylidene]hydrazine (**3c**) :

Yield : 64%, m.p. 162-165 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{12}N_5O_2SCl$: C, 44.24; H, 3.71; N, 21.49. Found : C, 44.21; H, 3.67; N, 21.41; IR (KBr) : 748 (C-Cl), 1568 (N=CH), 3378 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.54-2.60 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 2.98-3.04 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 7.38 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 7.75 (1H, s, NH), 8.02 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.12 (1H, s, NH), 7.13-7.94 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 38.5 (CH₂-NH), 48.3 (N-CH₂), 138.9 (C₄ of thiazole), 141.8 (C₅ of thiazole), 158.63 (N=CH), 174.1 (C₂ of thiazole), 126.6, 127.4, 128.9, 129.9, 135.5, 139.6 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 326 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-*N'*-[(2-chlorophenyl)methylidene]hydrazine (**3d**) :

Yield : 65%, m.p. 158-161 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{12}N_5O_2SCl$: C, 44.24; H, 3.71; N, 21.49. Found : C, 44.20; H, 3.66; N, 21.41; IR (KBr) : 748 (C-Cl), 1565 (N=CH), 3379 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.46-2.50 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 3.04-3.11 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 7.38 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 7.57 (1H, s, NH), 7.90 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.11 (1H, s, NH), 7.25-7.91 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 38.7 (CH₂-NH), 48.5 (N-CH₂), 138.7 (C₄ of thiazole), 142.9 (C₅ of thiazole), 157.6 (N=CH), 173.6 (C₂ of thiazole), 126.7, 128.9, 129.8, 130.6, 135.8, 137.8 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 326 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-*N'*-[(4-bromophenyl)methylidene]hydrazine (**3e**) :

Yield : 65%, m.p. 160–163 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₂N₅O₂SBr : C, 38.93; H, 3.26; N, 18.91. Found : C, 38.90; H, 3.22; N, 18.88; IR (KBr) : 639 (C-Br), 1567 (N=CH), 3368 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.45–2.50 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 2.90–2.95 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 7.29 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 7.84 (1H, s, NH), 7.97 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.15 (1H, s, NH), 7.32–7.65 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 39.7 (CH₂-NH), 46.3 (N-CH₂), 137.4 (C₄ of thiazole), 141.2 (C₅ of thiazole), 156.4 (N=CH), 168.6 (C₂ of thiazole), 125.8, 128.6, 135.8, 138.9. (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 370 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-*N'*-[(3-bromophenyl)methylidene]hydrazine (**3f**) :

Yield : 63%, m.p. 155–158 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₂N₅O₂SBr : C, 38.93; H, 3.26; N, 18.91. Found : C, 38.88; H, 3.21; N, 18.87; IR (KBr) : 652 (C-Br), 1576 (N=CH), 3372 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.54–2.60 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 2.92–2.98 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 7.22 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 7.81 (1H, s, NH), 7.92 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.14 (1H, s, NH), 7.21–7.92 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 39.4 (CH₂-NH), 49.7 (N-CH₂), 139.2 (C₄ of thiazole), 142.8 (C₅ of thiazole), 156.4 (N=CH), 172.4 (C₂ of thiazole), 126.6, 127.5, 128.7, 130.8, 135.6, 138.9 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 370 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-*N'*-[(2-bromophenyl)methylidene]hydrazine (**3g**) :

Yield : 64%, m.p. 152–154 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₂N₅O₂SBr : C, 38.93; H, 3.26; N, 18.91. Found : C, 38.89; H, 3.21; N, 18.88; IR (KBr) : 636 (C-Br), 1565 (N=CH), 3360 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.48–2.54 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 2.94–2.99 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 7.32 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 7.76 (1H, s, NH), 8.07 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.18 (1H, s, NH), 7.33–7.65 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 37.6 (CH₂-NH), 43.4 (N-CH₂), 140.2 (C₄ of thiazole), 141.6 (C₅ of thiazole), 154.6 (N=CH), 170.7 (C₂ of thiazole), 125.8, 127.9, 128.7, 129.8, 134.9, 137.8 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 370 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-*N'*-[(4-nitrophenyl)methylidene]hydrazine (**3h**) :

Yield : 66%, m.p. 175–178 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₂N₆O₄S : C, 42.85; H, 3.59; N, 24.98. Found : C,

42.80; H, 3.50; N, 24.92; IR (KBr) : 865 (C-N), 1549 (N=O), 1569 (N=CH), 3362 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.45–2.51 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 3.06–3.12 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 7.40 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 7.85 (1H, s, NH), 8.13 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.20 (1H, s, NH), 7.37–7.94 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 39.1 (CH₂-NH), 49.3 (N-CH₂), 140.6 (C₄ of thiazole), 142.7 (C₅ of thiazole), 154.9 (N=CH), 171.4 (C₂ of thiazole), 123.4, 127.7, 136.5, 148.6 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 336 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-*N'*-[(3-nitrophenyl)methylidene]hydrazine (**3i**) :

Yield : 61%, m.p. 170–173 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₂N₆O₄S : C, 42.85; H, 3.59; N, 24.98. Found : C, 42.81; H, 3.51; N, 24.90; IR (KBr) : 842 (C-N), 1520 (N=O), 1579 (N=CH), 3358 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.41–2.49 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 3.05–3.11 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 7.36 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 7.77 (1H, s, NH), 7.87 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.10 (1H, s, NH), 7.22–7.85 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 37.6 (CH₂-NH), 49.2 (N-CH₂), 140.4 (C₄ of thiazole), 141.3 (C₅ of thiazole), 157.7 (N=CH), 170.6 (C₂ of thiazole), 122.6, 125.8, 127.7, 128.9, 137.5, 149.8 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 336 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-*N'*-[(2-nitrophenyl)methylidene]hydrazine (**3j**) :

Yield : 60%, m.p. 168–171 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₂N₆O₄S : C, 42.85; H, 3.59; N, 24.98. Found : C, 42.81; H, 3.54; N, 24.92; IR (KBr) : 851 (C-N), 1544 (N=O), 1577 (N=CH), 3356 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.39–2.48 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 3.08–3.14 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 7.39 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 7.86 (1H, s, NH), 8.07 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.24 (1H, s, NH), 7.24–7.97 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 37.9 (CH₂-NH), 44.3 (N-CH₂), 139.9 (C₄ of thiazole), 142.6 (C₅ of thiazole), 157.6 (N=CH), 170.2 (C₂ of thiazole), 123.6, 125.9, 127.6, 128.8, 136.9, 148.8 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 336 M⁺.

General method for the synthesis of compounds 4(a-j) :

Compound **3a** (0.009 mol) and chloroacetyl chloride (0.009 mol) in the presence of Et₃N (0.009 mol) were dissolved in methanol at room temperature and allowed to react. The reaction mixture was first continuously stirred on a magnetic stirrer for about 2–3 h followed by reflux on a steam bath for about 1.30–4.15 h. The products

were cooled and filtered. The products were purified over a column chromatography and recrystallized from ethanol at room temperature to yield compound **4a**.

Compounds **4(b-j)** have also been synthesized by similar method as above.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(phenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxo-1-iminoazetidide (**4a**) :

Yield : 65%, m.p. 169–172 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{14}N_5O_3SCl$: C, 45.71; H, 3.83; N, 19.04. Found : C, 45.66; H, 3.78; N, 19.00; IR (KBr) : 1332 (C-N), 1742 (CO cyclic), 2917 (CH-Cl); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 2.49–2.55 (2H, m, CH_2 -NH), 2.97–3.02 (2H, m, N- CH_2), 4.56 (1H, d, *J* 5.0 Hz, CH-Cl), 5.12 (1H, d, *J* 5.0 Hz, N-CH), 7.38 (1H, s, C_4H of thiazole), 7.85 (1H, s, NH), 8.18 (1H, s, NH), 6.85–7.72 (5H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 37.3 (CH_2 -NH), 45.7 (N- CH_2), 52.2 (CH-Cl), 64.4 (N-CH), 138.4 (C_4 of thiazole), 140.2 (C_5 of thiazole), 170.2 (C_2 of thiazole), 173.7 (CO, cyclic), 126.6, 128.6, 129.6, 138.9 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB): 368 M^+ .

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxo-1-iminoazetidide (**4b**) :

Yield : 62%, m.p. 175–178 °C; Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{13}N_5O_3SCl_2$: C, 41.80; H, 3.25; N, 17.41. Found : C, 41.77; H, 3.21; N, 17.36; IR (KBr) : 769 (C-Cl), 1342 (C-N), 1748 (CO cyclic), 2919 (CH-Cl); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 2.51–2.60 (2H, m, CH_2 -NH), 3.05–3.12 (2H, m, N- CH_2), 4.52 (1H, d, *J* 4.95 Hz, CH-Cl), 5.16 (1H, d, *J* 4.95 Hz, N-CH), 7.29 (1H, s, C_4H of thiazole), 7.92 (1H, s, NH), 8.10 (1H, s, NH), 6.86–7.72 (4H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 37.5 (CH_2 -NH), 46.4 (N- CH_2), 52.8 (CH-Cl), 62.4 (N-CH), 139.4 (C_4 of thiazole), 141.2 (C_5 of thiazole), 170.6 (C_2 of thiazole), 176.2 (CO, cyclic), 126.5, 128.9, 135.7, 138.6 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 402 M^+ .

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(3-chlorophenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxo-1-iminoazetidide (**4c**) :

Yield : 65%, m.p. 173–176 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{13}N_5O_3SCl_2$: C, 41.80; H, 3.25; N, 17.41. Found : C, 41.75; H, 3.20; N, 17.34; IR (KBr) : 780 (C-Cl), 1352 (C-N), 1756 (CO, cyclic), 2923 (CH-Cl); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 2.50–2.58 (2H, m, CH_2 -NH), 2.99–3.08 (2H, m, N- CH_2), 4.58 (1H, d, *J* 5.05 Hz, CH-Cl), 5.16 (1H, d, *J* 5.05 Hz, N-CH), 7.25 (1H, s,

C_4H of thiazole), 7.89 (1H, s, NH), 8.15 (1H, s, NH), 6.79–7.64 (4H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 38.5 (CH_2 -NH), 47.4 (N- CH_2), 53.8 (CH-Cl), 65.9 (N-CH), 140.4 (C_4 of thiazole), 142.2 (C_5 of thiazole), 171.9 (C_2 of thiazole), 176.5 (CO, cyclic), 126.6, 127.8, 128.9, 129.7, 135.6, 138.8 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 402 M^+ .

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(2-chlorophenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxo-1-iminoazetidide (**4d**) :

Yield : 67%, m.p. 169–171 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{13}N_5O_3SCl_2$: C, 41.80; H, 3.25; N, 17.41. Found : C, 41.72; H, 3.18; N, 17.33; IR (KBr) : 779 (C-Cl), 1338 (C-N), 1752 (CO, cyclic), 2928 (CH-Cl); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 2.54–2.61 (2H, m, CH_2 -NH), 3.05–3.11 (2H, m, N- CH_2), 4.53 (1H, d, *J* 5.10 Hz, CH-Cl), 5.19 (1H, d, *J* 5.10 Hz, N-CH), 7.20 (1H, s, C_4H of thiazole), 7.88 (1H, s, NH), 8.12 (1H, s, NH), 6.81–7.62 (4H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 36.5 (CH_2 -NH), 46.2 (N- CH_2), 54.8 (CH-Cl), 62.4 (N-CH), 140.4 (C_4 of thiazole), 142.7 (C_5 of thiazole), 171.3 (C_2 of thiazole), 174.2 (CO, cyclic), 126.7, 128.2, 128.9, 129.8, 135.7, 138.8 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 402 M^+ .

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(4-bromophenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxo-1-iminoazetidide (**4e**) :

Yield : 62%, m.p. 183–186 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{13}N_5O_3SBrCl$: C, 37.64; H, 2.93; N, 15.67. Found : C, 37.60; H, 2.90; N, 15.61; IR (KBr) : 580 (C-Br), 1325 (C-N), 1749 (CO cyclic), 2892 (CH-Cl); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 2.51–2.55 (2H, m, CH_2 -NH), 2.99–3.05 (2H, m, N- CH_2), 4.52 (1H, d, *J* 5.15 Hz, CH-Cl), 5.12 (1H, d, *J* 5.15 Hz, N-CH), 7.28 (1H, s, C_4H of thiazole), 7.78 (1H, s, NH), 8.19 (1H, s, NH), 7.35–7.95 (4H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 38.3 (CH_2 -NH), 45.4 (N- CH_2), 47.8 (CH-Cl), 59.9 (N-CH), 140.8 (C_4 of thiazole), 142.7 (C_5 of thiazole), 171.7 (C_2 of thiazole), 174.3 (CO, cyclic), 126.5, 128.8, 135.9, 138.8 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 447 M^+ .

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(3-bromophenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxo-1-iminoazetidide (**4f**) :

Yield : 65%, m.p. 180–182 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{13}N_5O_3SBrCl$: C, 37.64; H, 2.93; N, 15.67. Found : C, 37.59; H, 2.89; N, 15.63; IR (KBr) : 581 (C-Br), 1328 (C-N), 1748 (CO cyclic), 2892 (CH-Cl); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 2.57–2.64 (2H, m, CH_2 -NH), 2.93–2.99 (2H, m, N- CH_2), 4.45 (1H, d, *J* 5.15 Hz, CH-

Cl), 5.17 (1H, d, *J* 5.15 Hz, N-CH), 7.30 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 7.85 (1H, s, NH), 8.24 (1H, s, NH), 7.31–7.92 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 37.5 (CH₂-NH), 46.4 (N-CH₂), 49.7 (CH-Cl), 59.9 (N-CH), 140.6 (C₄ of thiazole), 141.6 (C₅ of thiazole), 170.8 (C₂ of thiazole), 175.3 (CO, cyclic), 126.8, 127.8, 128.9, 129.6, 135.7, 138.9 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 447 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(2-bromophenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxo-1-iminoazetidide (**4g**) :

Yield : 65%, m.p. 178–180 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₃N₅O₃SBrCl : C, 37.64; H, 2.93; N, 15.67. Found : C, 37.60; H, 2.91; N, 15.64; IR (KBr) : 566 (C-Br), 1334 (C-N), 1755 (CO, cyclic), 2884 (CH-Cl); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.52–2.60 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 2.97–3.07 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 4.56 (1H, d, *J* 5.20 Hz, CH-Cl), 5.15 (1H, d, *J* 5.20 Hz, N-CH), 7.27 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 8.00 (1H, s, NH), 8.22 (1H, s, NH), 7.27–7.84 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 39.3 (CH₂-NH), 47.6 (N-CH₂), 48.7 (CH-Cl), 58.7 (N-CH), 139.4 (C₄ of thiazole), 141.8 (C₅ of thiazole), 170.6 (C₂ of thiazole), 172.5 (CO, cyclic), 126.6, 128.1, 128.9, 129.7, 135.8, 138.6 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 447 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(4-nitrophenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxo-1-iminoazetidide (**4h**) :

Yield : 62%, m.p. 187–189 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₃N₆O₅SCl : C, 40.73; H, 3.17; N, 20.35. Found : C, 40.70; H, 3.12; N, 20.31; IR (KBr) : 874 (C-NO), 1359 (C-N), 2932 (CH-Cl), 1542 (NO₂), 1747 (CO, cyclic); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.50–2.58 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 3.10–3.16 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 4.48 (1H, d, *J* 5.15 Hz, CH-Cl), 5.13 (1H, d, *J* 5.15 Hz, N-CH), 7.24 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 8.03 (1H, s, NH), 8.25 (1H, s, NH), 7.1–7.71 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 35.1 (CH₂-NH), 46.8 (N-CH₂), 49.6 (CH-Cl), 64.8 (N-CH), 140.4 (C₄ of thiazole), 142.9 (C₅ of thiazole), 170.6 (C₂ of thiazole), 174.9 (CO, cyclic), 125.8, 128.5, 137.7, 149.9 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 413 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxo-1-iminoazetidide (**4i**) :

Yield : 64%, m.p. 183–187 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₃N₆O₅SCl : C, 40.73; H, 3.17; N, 20.35. Found : C, 40.71; H, 3.14; N, 20.32; IR (KBr) : 868 (C-NO), 1367 (C-N), 1549 (NO₂), 1752 (CO, cyclic), 2924 (CH-Cl); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.49–2.56 (2H, m,

CH₂-NH), 2.92–2.99 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 4.49 (1H, d, *J* 5.00 Hz, CH-Cl), 5.02 (1H, d, *J* 5.00 Hz, N-CH), 7.36 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 7.95 (1H, s, NH), 8.17 (1H, s, NH), 7.16–7.79 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 38.7 (CH₂-NH), 46.8 (N-CH₂), 52.6 (CH-Cl), 61.8 (N-CH), 140.4 (C₄ of thiazole), 142.7 (C₅ of thiazole), 170.5 (C₂ of thiazole), 173.6 (CO, cyclic), 122.4, 125.6, 127.8, 128.9, 137.8, 149.7 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 413 M⁺.

N-[2-(2-Amino-5-nitrothiazolyl)ethyl]-4-(2-nitrophenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxo-1-iminoazetidide (**4j**) :

Yield : 62%, m.p. 181–184 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₃N₆O₅SCl : C, 40.73; H, 3.17; N, 20.35. Found : C, 40.69; H, 3.10; N, 20.28; IR (KBr) : 875 (C-NO), 1362 (C-N), 1546 (NO₂), 1768 (CO, cyclic), 2926 (CH-Cl); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.52–2.60 (2H, m, CH₂-NH), 3.06–3.14 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 4.50 (1H, d, *J* 5.15 Hz, CH-Cl), 5.08 (1H, d, *J* 5.15 Hz, N-CH), 7.31 (1H, s, C₄H of thiazole), 8.01 (1H, s, NH), 8.19 (1H, s, NH), 7.05–7.71 (4H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 39.4 (CH₂-NH), 47.2 (N-CH₂), 53.6 (CH-Cl), 61.8 (N-CH), 140.7 (C₄ of thiazole), 143.2 (C₅ of thiazole), 171.3 (C₂ of thiazole), 172.9 (CO, cyclic), 122.6, 125.5, 127.8, 128.9, 137.7, 149.8 (Ar-C); Mass (FAB) : 413 M⁺.

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